

DNA Binding Properties of Some Cationic Acridine Derivatives[†]

SANTANU BHATTACHARYA* and MINI THOMAS

Department of Organic Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore-560 012

Manuscript received 17 August 1998

Four cationic acridine derivatives have been synthesized. The positively charged amine residue in one of these is connected directly on to the acridine nucleus and in three other acridines, the amines are connected via a 9-CH₂ unit to acridine. We have investigated the binding of these acridines with mammalian DNA by absorption titration, UV- and induced-CD spectroscopy and competitive ethidium bromide displacement fluorescence assay. The effects on the DNA-duplex denaturation melting temperatures upon binding of each one of these are also examined. The results obtained herein clearly show that the introduction of a -CH₂ group in the immediate vicinity of the intercalation moiety introduces alterations in the DNA binding characteristics of the resulting acridines.

One of the important aspects in the design of new therapeutic agents involves adequate understanding of the structural and thermodynamic aspects of the interactions between a drug and the target biological macromolecule. In this direction binding of a number of potential drug molecules with DNA has been studied as part of the attempts to improve the design of potential antitumor agents¹. It has been realized that many cytostatic drugs interact with DNA usually by intercalation or through minor groove binding, cross-linking or a combination of these modalities². In this regard the use of acridine derivatives in various pharmacological applications is noteworthy³. Acridines and their derivatives are among the most widely used class of antimalarials known even from the early part of the nineteenth century⁴. Since then several acridine derivatives have been developed that are endowed with significant DNA-binding⁵ and cross-linking^{6a,6b} properties. Some of these examples include *m*-amsacrine³, and a number of poly-intercalating dimeric and trimeric acridines^{6a} and acridine linked nitrogen mustards^{6b}. Notably *m*-amsacrine was the first synthetic DNA intercalator to find widespread clinical use. It induces chromosomal aberrations and sister chromatid exchange and inhibits topoisomerase II⁵. In the pursuit of achieving numerous objectives such as better nucleic acid affinity⁸, anti-tumor activity⁷, or circumvention of drug resistance⁹, acridine attached oligopeptides⁸, dimeric and trimeric acridines attached via rigid linkers⁷, and modified amsacrines⁹ have been developed. In addition, there are many reports in the recent literature that describe the preparation and activity of acridine attached photonucleases¹⁰, bleomycin analogs¹¹, ribonuclease mimics¹² etc. Finally, the interesting physico-chemical properties of acridines make them useful probes for DNA structure and dynamics.

Due to our continuing interest in the development of novel chemical nucleases and DNA recognizing molecules¹³ we considered the following aspects prior undertaking an

elaborate synthetic programme involving acridine analogs. We thought that the presence of an intercalator residue in a molecule, and its anchoring through a recognition element like a peptide of specific sequence or other known DNA binding residues such as netropsin will ensure tight and sequence selective binding with DNA. Tethering such a molecule finally with a chemical (redox)¹³ or photochemically activatable DNA cleavage moiety^{10,14} should provide new systems with attractive biological properties. During the course of such studies involving the preparation of acridine analogs, we found that even simple 9-substituted-acridine derivatives offer differential DNA recognition properties. Especially it was realized that a subtle change in the substitution characteristic on the acridine system brings about substantial changes in their DNA interacting abilities. In this report, we present the DNA binding properties of some of these simple 9-substituted-acridine derivatives by absorption titrimetry, circular dichroism spectroscopy, thermal duplex denaturation studies and ethidium displacement assay. The intrinsic binding constants of these acridines were estimated from absorption titrations employing the half-reciprocal approach as described previously¹⁵.

Results and Discussion

Structural considerations in acridine synthesis : As reported in the literature, with majority of the acridine derivatives the functionalization has been achieved by reacting the appropriate amine component with 9-chloroacridine in phenol at 110°, where the reaction proceeds via the intermediacy of 9-phenoxyacridine¹⁶. After this step, a base treatment is usually necessary¹⁶ and hence this method suffers from the disadvantage while working with acid-labile or base-labile groups which are often encountered in peptide chemistry. In order to circumvent this, we tried to exploit the reactivity of 9-bormomethylacridine (9-BMA) in the preparation of various acridine-based systems. We found

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

that 9-BMA reacts conveniently with primary, secondary as well as tertiary amines in common, polar organic solvents such as acetone, acetonitrile or methanol at room temperature giving the desired products in good yields.

In addition to the improved reactivity of the above acridine derivatives, this type of substitution brings about additional steric and electronic constraints in the immediate vicinity of the DNA intercalation site owing to the presence of a $-CH_2$ unit at position-9 in the place of the $-NH-$ group in the case of widely investigated 9-aminoacridine derivatives. The presence of a 9- NH_2 substituent in acridines significantly influences the electronic properties of the acridine chromophore as illustrated by the marked shift in the pK_a of the ring 'N' from ~ 3.5 to ~ 8.3 as one goes from *N*-[2-(dimethylamino)ethyl]acridine-4-carboxamide (DACA, an acridine that is in clinical trials against cancer) to *N*-[2-(dimethylamino)ethyl]-9-aminoacridine-4-carboxamide (AAC). These changes in pK_a values imply that the ring N of the latter acridine (AAC) should remain protonated at physiological pH and thus will be bis-cationic.

Crenshaw *et al.*¹⁷ examined the thermodynamic properties associated with the interaction of DACA and AAC using absorption spectroscopy and found that the placement of the $-NH_2$ moiety at C-9 results in ~ 6 -fold enhancement in the DNA binding affinity. In the light of these considerations, it occurred to us that probing the DNA binding characteristics of the newly developed acridines is worthwhile to pursue. 9-Pyridinium acridine chloride (CA-I) in which the positive charge is directly attached to C-9 has been used as a control for evaluating the nature of binding of the newly developed acridines where the cationic substituent at the 9-position is separated from the acridine nucleus by a $-CH_2$ group.

The synthesis of 9-pyridinium acridine chloride began with the preparation of 9-chloroacridine which was synthesized from anthranilic acid through the intermediacy of *N*-phenylanthranilic acid^{18a}. Spectral, analytical data and melting point for this compound matched with those reported in literature^{18b}. 9-Pyridinium acridine chloride (CA-I) was synthesized¹⁹ by quaternization of pyridine with 9-chloroacridine in excess pyridine and the product (80% yield) obtained was recrystallized from ethanol/benzene mixture. *N,N,N*-Trimethylammonium-*N*-9-methylacridine bromide (BA-I) was prepared by the treatment of 9-bromomethylacridine with Me_3N in dry acetone as described in Scheme 1. 9-Bromomethylacridine in turn was synthesized upon adaptation of procedure of Akasaka *et al.* from 9-methylacridine²⁰, which was prepared from *N,N*-diphenylamine according to the procedure described²¹. Similarly, 9-

pyridinium *N*-methylacridine bromide (BA-II) and 9-(4,4'-bipyridinium)methylacridine bromide (BA-III) were synthesized by treatment of 9-bromomethylacridine with pyridine and 4,4'-bipyridine respectively. All the final reaction products and intermediates gave the expected spectral and analytical characteristics consistent with their structures.

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions : (a) $POCl_3$, 140° , 4 h, (b) dry pyridine, 100° , 30 min, (c) anh. $ZnCl_2$, CH_3CO_2H , 220° , 6 h, (d) NBS, CCl_4 , reflux, 8 h, (e) $(CH_3)_3N$, dry acetone, RT, 30 min, (f) dry pyridine, 100° , 30 min, (g) 4,4'-bipyridine, 120° , 30 min.

Absorption titrations : Under the present experimental conditions, the presence of aromatic nucleobases with stacking abilities and outside negative charges (phosphodiester anions of the backbone) in duplex DNA offers scope for intercalative as well as electrostatic modes of binding for the cationic acridines that contain planar aromatic rings. Intercalation involves insertion of the planar acridines between the base pairs of DNA in a position approximately perpendicular to the helix axis. To examine this aspect, the interaction of acridine derivatives with duplex DNA was examined by monitoring the changes in the UV-VIS spectra of the acridines upon addition of CT DNA. Fig. 1 shows the absorption spectra of the various acridine derivatives in the absence and presence of varying amounts of CT DNA. All the acridine derivatives show fine-structured absorption bands. The binding of the acridine derivatives to duplex DNA led to strong decrease in the absorption intensities with small extent of red-shift in the absorption maxima of the acridines. It is clear that the progressive addition of DNA leads to strong hypochromism in the absorption intensity in all the four cases. The percentage hypochromism calculated as % hypochromism = $[\epsilon_{free} - \epsilon_{apparent}] / [\epsilon_{free} - \epsilon_{bound}]$ ca. 52, 45, 41 and 60% for CA-I, BA-I, BA-II and BA-III respec-

Fig 1 Absorption titrations of different acridines with CT DNA Trace 1 in all the panels show the uv-vis spectra due to the acridines alone Subsequent traces were obtained upon incremental addition of CT DNA as shown Insets show the plots of the relative optical densities (A_0/A) vs [DNA]

tively. Spectra obtained upon complex formation with CT DNA by each of the acridines exhibit clear isosbestic points around 400 nm. The presence of an isosbestic point in each of these titrations clearly suggests that there exists an equilibrium between the free and the bound ligands. Furthermore, this also implies that the ligands have no spectroscopically detectable intermediate states in the presence of DNA. The manifestation of strong hypochromicity in the uv-vis band of each acridine is a definitive evidence of intense interaction between the electronic states of DNA and that of the ligand chromophore.

It is instructive to compare the present results of the absorption titrations of DNA with some of the more thoroughly studied acridines. The absorption spectrum of 9-aminoacridine-DNA complex reported by Yamaoka and Ransic^{17a} is quite similar to that obtained in the present case except that the λ_{max} observed with 9-aminoacridine-DNA complex is about 4 nm more red-shifted. The abs. spectra obtained in the titration of CT DNA with the present acridines are also

quite similar to that obtained on binding of DACA with DNA^{17b}. Furthermore, the association constants of these acridines are of the same order of DACA or 9-aminoacridine which is not unexpected when one considers the fact that either type of acridines are monocationic.

Ethidium bromide displacement assay : Quenching of DNA bound ethidium bromide (EB) fluorescence has been used as a diagnostic tool for the evaluation of the binding of various types ligands to DNA, including polyintercalating acridine derivatives^{22a}, and groove binders^{22b}. All the acridines studied in the present case quenched the fluorescence of DNA bound EB, indicating gradual displacement of the intercalated EB (not shown). Similar quenching of EB-DNA fluorescence by acridine derivatives has been reported by Gaugain *et al.*^{22a}. Since the fluorescence enhancement of EB is due to the intercalative binding of this ligand to DNA, quenching of EB fluorescence by the cationic acridines studied in the present case essentially implies that these molecules compete with EB for binding with DNA by some modes other than just electrostatic interactions.

Fig. 2. Half-reciprocal plots for binding of different acridine derivatives with CT DNA. Panels A-D correspond to plots due to the DNA binding of CA-I, BA-I, BA-II and BA-III respectively.

Thermal denaturation studies : It is well known that molecules which bind to DNA by intercalation, groove binding or electrostatic interaction, stabilize DNA duplex against thermal denaturation. For molecules which interact solely by electrostatic interactions, this stabilization is highly salt-dependent since the double helix gets stabilized by charge neutralization in the presence of the metal ions of the salt. Most of the molecules which interact with DNA by intercalation are positively charged planar aromatic compounds and therefore the duplex stabilization in such cases are partly due to electrostatic reasons and partly due to the stacking of the aromatic parts of the guest molecule into the DNA base pairs. The effects of various acridine derivatives on the helix-to-coil transition of CT DNA were measured at 18 mM NaCl concentration in SSC buffer. All the acridines studied herein increase the T_m of DNA. In addition, all of them exhibit a hypochromic change on heating before the thermal transition. This effect is most pronounced in the case of BA-I. This absorbance decrease could be due to the fact that part of the partially intercalated acridine molecules undergoes reorientations while the DNA base pair arrangements 'loosen' during the pre-melting stage.

CD measurements : After examining the effects on DNA upon binding of acridines by absorption spectroscopy, we then turned our attention to the circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy. CD, defined as the differential absorbance of the left and the right circularly polarized light was used to obtain additional insight concerning the DNA recognition of the acridine derivatives used in this study. Fig. 3 shows the effects of addition of increasing amounts of CA-I and BA-I into constant concentrations of DNA. Both the acridines enhance the ultraviolet CD (UV CD) of B-DNA

with CA-I having a greater effect compared to BA-I at a given D/P ratio as evident from the plot of molar ellipticity values of the resultant complexes as a function of added ligand (Figs. 3A and 3B inset). The positive band of the DNA doublet is affected more in comparison to the negative band. At the maximum D/P values as indicated in Fig. 3, the positive band is blue-shifted by about 10 nm in both the cases, whereas the negative band shows red-shift of approximately 3 nm. In the case of both the complexes, there is ca. 7 nm blue-shift of the crossover point of the DNA band.

Fig. 3. UV-CD studies. (A) Effect of addition of CA-I on the UV-CD of CT DNA ($133 \mu\text{M}$) in SSC buffer. (B) Effect of addition of BA-I on the UV-CD of CT DNA ($133 \mu\text{M}$). Plots of molar ellipticity vs D/P are given in the inset of each panel.

The strong enhancement in the magnitude of the DNA doublet in the UV CD could be the result of interaction through gradual alteration of DNA structure. Since base pairs must separate vertically to allow for intercalation, the sugar phosphate backbone is disturbed and the regular helical structure is modified. There could be additional interactions between the ligand transition dipoles with that DNA. 9-Aminoacridine and proflavin have also been reported to enhance the UV CD of DNA without perturbing the regular doublet form^{23a}. In view of the similarity of the UV CD proflavine and 9-aminoacridine complexes, which have different substituents on the acridine ring and thus having dif-

ferent binding modes, Dalgleish and Peacocke^{23a} had proposed that the observed enhancement of the CD bands with increasing concentration of the acridines could be due to the shielding of DNA base pairs from one another. In fact Johnson and Tinoco^{23b} has shown that the magnitude of CD spectrum of DNA is anomalously low due to the cancellation of the rotational strengths of the many CD bands. To complicate the situation further, the change in CD in the short wavelength region could also be due to an ICD of the bound ligand. In the present case, the most remarkable difference between the CD spectra of the two complexes is the presence of a prominent shoulder at ~ 275 nm in the case of BA-I DNA complex, clearly indicating that there is some degree of difference in the nature of the two acridine-DNA complexes. Since the origin of ICD in the uv-region is still not clear^{23c}, we restrict our conclusion to saying that the nature of the two complexes seems to be different.

All the ligands investigated in this study are achiral and therefore cannot exhibit any CD signal on their own. Upon binding to DNA by partial or complete intercalation, the ligands experience a chiral environment, which results in the manifestation of the induced CD (ICD) signals in the ligand absorption region of the CD spectrum. Fig. 4 shows the effect of addition of increasing amounts of ligands to fixed concentration of DNA. As the ligand concentrations increase, the resultant CD signals increase in intensity. In all the cases where the acridine nucleus and the positive charge are separated by a methylene group, the CD band with the higher wavelength is found to be positive in sign

and the CD λ_{\max} is the same as that of the respective absorption maxima of the corresponding DNA-ligand complexes. It is important to note that the ICD spectrum manifested by CA-I in which the acridine moiety is directly attached to the positively charged centre is drastically different from the previously mentioned compounds. With CA-I, there is a negative band with a maximum at ~ 390 nm in addition to a positive band having the same CD λ_{\max} as that of its absorption band. Thus the ICD measurements support the hypothesis that the binding modes of the two types of acridines are different.

The intercalation of a ligand into DNA double helix generally induces a red-shift in the absorption maximum of the ligand, hypochromism of the absorption band, induced circular dichroism in the ligand absorption region, an altered ellipticity in the uv-region²⁴. Even though the binding of the acridine derivatives investigated in the present study is marked by considerable hypochromism of the ligand absorption band, there is practically no red-shift of the absorption maxima. The presence of CH_2 -substituents in the immediate vicinity of the intercalation moiety precludes the complete insertion of the planar aromatic acridine moiety into the base pairs of DNA. Additional support for partial intercalation stems from the thermal denaturation experiments. All the acridine-DNA complexes show further hypochromism on heating prior to melting. This implies that the partially intercalated ligand chromophores undergo re-orientation, most probably greater stacking into the base pairs of DNA at higher temperatures.

Fig. 4. ICD spectra obtained on binding of different acridine derivatives with CT DNA. Panels (A-D) correspond to spectra due to the DNA binding of BA-I, CA-I, BA-II and BA-III respectively. These spectra were obtained by adding increasing amounts of acridines to a constant concentration ($64 \mu\text{M}$) of CT DNA.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF DNA TITRATIONS WITH ACRIDINE DERIVATIVES AS REVEALED FROM THE UV-VIS, CD AND FROM THE EXPERIMENTS INVOLVING THE EFFECTS ON THERMAL DUPLEX DENATURATION TEMPERATURE (T_m) OF DNA

Compd.	λ_{\max} (nm)/ (ϵ)	% Hypo- chromism	$10^{-4}K(M^{-1})$	ICD (Sign) nm	ΔT_m °C
CA-I	367 (13400)	52	0.57	393 (-) 365 (+)	6.0
BA-I	365 (7100)	45	1.8	365 (+)	7.0
BA-II	365 (11400)	41	2.58	365 (+)	8.0
BA-III	365 (13400)	60	1.04	376 (+)	5.0

Since hypochromism is a manifestation of stacking interactions, there is enough reason to believe that there is at least partial stacking with all the four acridines studied here which show substantial hypochromism (Table 1). The fact that all the cationic acridines increase the T_m of CT DNA at moderately high salt concentrations (18 mM) further suggests that the binding is not entirely electrostatic. The dissociation constants calculated by the half-reciprocal plot method are in the order of 10^{-4} which is also supportive of a partial intercalation hypothesis.

Ethidium bromide displacement assay has also been used by a number of researchers to estimate the DNA binding efficiency of different class of DNA binding molecules^{22a,b}. All the cationic acridines used in this study displace EB from DNA as measured by the reduction in fluorescence intensity of DNA bound EB. From the concentration of the acridine necessary for 50% reduction in fluorescence intensity the relative binding constants have been calculated. The binding constants obtained from the competition experiments are slightly higher than the ones obtained from absorption measurements (not shown)^{22c}. However, these values are within an order of magnitude of the values obtained from absorption titration.

Absorption and fluorescence measurements do not suggest any considerable difference regarding the binding modes of these compounds. The first noticeable difference in the modes of binding came from circular dichromism measurements in the DNA region (UV-CD). CA-I and BA-I were the acridine derivatives used for these experiments. The first one has no methylene group connecting the acridine moiety and the cationic centre whereas the second one has. BA-I is also having a bulky quaternary ammonium moiety close to the intercalation site. This acridine was chosen for CD measurements in the DNA region as it shows the largest pre-melting hypochromism during melting temperature measurements among the acridine derivatives having the methylene

bridge. Both the acridines increase the magnitude of the DNA band. The major difference between the two complexes is the presence of a shoulder around 270 nm in the case of BA-I-CT DNA complex implying some degree of difference between the two complexes. Additional support for this hypothesis comes from induced CD measurements. All the three acridine derivatives which have got methylene groups between the acridine moiety and the cationic centre show positive induced CD with a maximum, same as that of the corresponding absorption spectrum of the acridine-DNA complex. CA-I which does not possess a methylene group between the acridine moiety and the positively charged centre on the other hand manifests an ICD doublet band with both halves of the doublet having comparable intensity. The negative half of this doublet appears about 20 nm red-shifted from the absorption maximum of BA-I DNA complex. The positive half of the doublet corresponds to the absorption spectrum of the complex between this acridine and DNA.

In all the four cases of acridine-DNA complexes the magnitude of ICD increases as the amount of acridine increases. From the circular dichromism studies of aminoacridines bound to DNA, Dalglish *et al.*^{26a} proposed that two possible explanations could be advanced for the observed variation of ICD as a function of acridine concentration. (1) The variation is the result of interaction between bound ligands, which naturally increases as the number of molecules in a given interacting group increases. This kind of interaction between bound ligands will result in the formation of exciton bands. (2) The progressive binding of ligand molecules continuously alter the shape of the macromolecule, so that the environment of any particular bound ligand is determined by the number of bound ligand molecules in its vicinity. On this basis, the cause of the induced optical activity is the interaction of the ligands with the DNA bases surrounding them, rather than with the other ligands. Among all the acridines studied by these authors, with the exception of proflavine, none of the aminoacridines show a doublet of positive and negative peaks which would be expected for exciton splitting. The bands observed for proflavine are of unequal intensity and therefore the exciton bands, if they are formed, must be extremely non-conservative. The negative band in this case could also be due the partial occupation of GC sites. The CD spectrum of 2,7-dibutylproflavin, which binds to DNA by partial intercalation on the other hand, exhibits a single positive band in the visible region which increases in magnitude as a function of ligand concentration^{26b}.

The sign of ICD has been used for assigning the base specificity by a number of researchers. Carvlin *et al.*^{27a,b}

studied the interaction of a series of mesosubstituted porphyrins with CT DNA and oligonucleotides by hydrodynamic measurements and circular dichroism studies. Pasternack *et al.*^{25a} investigated the interactions of tetrakis(4-*N*-methylpyridyl)porphine (H₂TMPyP-4) and its copper(II), nickel(II), zinc(II), cobalt(III), iron(III), and manganese(III) derivatives with CT DNA and oligonucleotides. All the metalloporphyrins which do not have axial ligands (Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}) and also the non-metalated porphyrin show negative ICD with poly(dG-dC) in the ligand absorption region. Those metalloporphyrins that maintain axial ligands display either no CD spectrum at all or small positive bands. All of the porphyrins examined display large positive CD spectra, with poly(dA-dT), except the Ni^{II} derivative, which has a conservative spectrum. The complexes formed with poly(dA-dT) with axially bound metalloporphyrins may not be due to complete intercalation. Even then, they must involve more than purely electrostatic forces, since if that were the case similar complexes would be expected with poly(dG-dC). Thus the metalloporphyrins with axial ligands must be partially interacted in the complex with poly(dA-dT). The ICD spectrum of Cu(II)TMPyP-4 and H₂TMPyP-4 with CT DNA are composed of both positive and negative bands, similar to the spectrum observed for proflavine which intercalates into AT and GC sites. The ICD profile obtained by these authors for zinc(II), cobalt(II), iron(III) derivatives of H₂TMPyP-4 are comparable to that for di-*t*-butylproflavine^{26b}, whose bulky tertiary-butyl groups prevent intercalation and which shows a marked specificity for AT rich DNA^{25b}. Thus, in combination with absorption spectral measurements, a negative ICD has been taken as an indication of intercalative GC binding and a positive ICD as that of partial intercalation or external binding to AT regions^{25a}.

In the present case, 9-pyridinium acridine (CA-I) gives an ICD composed of both positive and negative bands of almost equal intensity upon binding with CT DNA which has ~42% GC content. This conservative ICD band could be due to exciton splitting arising from the interaction of the electronic levels of partially stacked acridines on DNA duplex, as in this case the pyridinium substituent which is nearly perpendicular to the plane of acridine moiety would prevent complete intercalation. On the other hand, the binding of 9-pyridinium methylacridine to DNA produces an ICD having a major positive band and a smaller negative band. Thus the introduction of a -CH₂ group at 9-position of acridine clearly alters the binding characteristics. Examination of the ICD obtained for BA-I/DNA complex shows that the introduction of Me₃N⁺ group close to the -CH₂ bridge leads to a complete disappearance of the negative

band. For BA-III, which has a still bulkier substituent, the ICD band corresponding to the λ_{\max} of the bound ligand shows a band that is positive in sign and also a small negative band at a higher wavelength. In conclusion, the results obtained herein clearly suggest that the introduction of a -CH₂ group in the immediate vicinity of the intercalation moiety introduces alterations in the DNA binding characteristics of the resulting acridines. Increasing the bulk of the substituent drives the binding more towards AT sequences. The observation that sterically more hindered acridines preferentially bind to AT sites is in good agreement with the fact that AT base pairs are more flexible than their GC counterparts²⁸ and thus can accommodate a more sterically demanding ligands without suffering from gross distortion of the native DNA structures²⁸.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra with a Jeol FX-90 (90 MHz) spectrometer in the appropriate deuterated solvent and the chemical shifts are given in ppm relative to an internal standard Me₄Si. Elemental analyses were performed by Microanalytical Division of the Department of Organic Chemistry and were run on a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyzer.

All the compounds and buffer agents used were purchased from best known suppliers and used as received; solvents were purified and dried by standard methods. Millipore grade water was used for all measurements. Calf thymus DNA (CT DNA) (Sigma) was purified by phenol-chloroform extraction followed by ethanol precipitation as described previously^{15,29}. Solutions of CT DNA in 3.3 mM sodium chloride, sodium citrate buffer (SSC buffer) (pH ~7.3) gave a uv absorbance ratio of $A_{260}/A_{280} > 1.9$.

9-*N,N,N*-Trimethylammonium-*N*-methylacridine bromide (BA-I) : 9-Bromomethylacridine (272 mg, 1 mmol) was added to a saturated solution of trimethylamine in acetone (prepared by dissolving dry (CH₃)₃N gas in cold acetone). The resulting mixture was stirred for 30 min in a sealed tube at 0°. The resulting light yellow solid was filtered, washed with dry acetone and dried under vacuum, (281 mg, 85%), m.p. 165° (Found : C, 55.1; H, 6.2; N, 7.9. C₁₇H₁₉N₂Br.2H₂O calcd. for : C, 55.5; H, 6.3; N, 7.7%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3400, 3200, 1650, 1370, 970, 940, 880, 770, 740 cm⁻¹; δ (90 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 3.0 (9H, s, 3×CH₃), 5.8 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.6–8.9 (8H, m, ArH); HPLC : C₁₆-reverse phase column, methanol/water; retention time, 8.7 min, single peak.

9-Pyridinium *N*-methylacridine bromide (BA-II) : 9-

Bromomethylacridine (272 mg, 1 mmol) was added to dry pyridine (4 ml) and the mixture was heated at 110° for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and dry benzene (8 ml) was added to it. The resulting solid was filtered, washed successively with chloroform and acetone and finally dried under reduced pressure (280 mg, 80%), m.p. 192° (Found : C, 61.8; H, 4.1; N, 7.4. C₁₉H₁₅N₂Br.H₂O calcd. for : C, 61.8; H, 4.6; N, 7.6%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3450, 3200, 1620, 1550, 1510, 1490, 1370, 1200, 1020, 820, 760, 750, 700 cm⁻¹; δ (90 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 6.5 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.5–8.7 (13H, m, ArH); HPLC : C₁₆-reverse phase column, methanol/water; retention time, 6.5 min, single peak.

9-(4,4'-Bipyridiniumyl)methylacridine bromide (BA-III) : A mixture of 9-bromomethylacridine (272 mg, 1 mmol) and 4,4'-bipyridine (156 mg, 1 mmol) was heated at 120° for 30 min whereupon the mixture first melted and then solidified. It was cooled to room temperature, washed successively with chloroform and acetone and dried under reduced pressure, (299 mg, 70%), m.p. 115° (Found : C, 55.4; H, 4.9; N, 7.9. C₂₄H₁₈N₃Br.5H₂O calcd. for : C, 55.6; H, 5.4; N, 8.1%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3360, 3200, 1630, 1600, 1400, 1270, 1220, 1150, 820, 750, 730, 700 cm⁻¹; δ (90 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 7.0 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.6–9.1 (16H, m, ArH); HPLC : C₁₆-reverse phase column, CH₃CN/water/0.1% TFA; retention time, 8.4 min, single peak.

Absorption spectral titrations : Absorption spectra were recorded on Shimadzu UV 2100 spectrophotometer. Quartz cells of 1 cm path-length were used and the measurements were carried out at 25° and pH 7.3 in 3.3 mM sodium chloride-sodium citrate (SSC) buffer unless otherwise mentioned. Concentrations of DNA calculated in base molarities were determined spectrophotometrically with $\epsilon_{260} = 6600 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Acridine concentrations were also determined similarly using the ϵ values given in Table 1. Titrations were carried out by keeping the concentration of the probe constant, while adding concentrated solution of the CT DNA in progressively increasing amounts into both cuvettes till the saturation in hypochromism was observed.

The intrinsic binding constant (K) for a given complex with DNA was obtained from a plot of $D/\Delta\epsilon_{\text{app}}$ vs D according to equation, $D/\Delta\epsilon_{\text{app}} = D/\Delta\epsilon + 1/(\Delta\epsilon K)$, where D is the concentration of DNA in base molarities, $\Delta\epsilon_{\text{app}} = |\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f|$ and $\Delta\epsilon_a = |\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f|$, where ϵ_b and ϵ_f are the respective extinction coefficients of the complex in the presence and absence of DNA. The apparent extinction coefficient, ϵ_{app} was obtained from $A_{\text{obs}}/[\text{acridine}]$. The data were fitted to the equation, with a slope equal to $1/\Delta\epsilon$ and y -intercept equal to $1/(\Delta\epsilon K)$. The intrinsic binding constant (K) was determined from the ratio of the slope to y -intercept¹⁵.

T_m measurements : T_m measurements were performed

by following the changes in optical densities at 260 nm as a function of temperature and a DNA : ligand ratio of 3 : 1 was used in all the cases. All the measurements were done on a Shimadzu UV 2100 spectrophotometer and the temperatures were maintained using a Julabo F25 water-circulator. Solutions were taken in quartz cuvettes stoppered with teflon caps. All the measurements were done in SSC buffer containing 18 mM NaCl at pH 7.3. The absorption intensities at 260 nm were plotted against individual temperatures in the presence of each ligand, and the midpoints of inflection regions in the temperature vs A_{260} curves were taken as the corresponding T_m values.

CD measurements : CD spectra were recorded on a JASCO J-500A spectropolarimeter and the data were processed by means of a JASCO-DP-501N data processor. In the case of UV CD measurements, the CD values were expressed as molar ellipticity, $[\theta]$ by following the equation, $[\theta] = [100 \text{ observed ellipticity (deg)/}l \times c] \text{ deg cm}^2 \text{ dmol}^{-1}$, where θ is the observed ellipticity in degrees, l the path-length of the cell in centimeters and c the concentration of DNA in base molarity. All measurements were done in 3.3 mM SSC buffer in quartz cells of 1 cm path length at pH 7.3 and 25°. Titrations in the DNA region (UV CD) were carried out by adding progressively increasing amounts of ligand to a solution of DNA of constant concentration. For the induced CD (ICD) measurements, increasing amounts of ligand was added to a constant concentration of DNA. Each spectrum is the average of four independent scans in the case of ICD measurements.

Ethidium bromide displacement assay : The competitive binding constants of different acridines with DNA were estimated by monitoring the effect of addition of various concentrations of cationic acridines on the fluorescence emission of intercalatively bound ethidium bromide-DNA complex. Fluorescence spectra were recorded on a Hitachi F-4500 fluorescence spectrophotometer. Temperature of the cuvette chamber was maintained using a Julabo F 10 water-circulating bath. All the measurements were done at 25° and pH 7.3 in 9.9 mM SSC buffer containing 9 mM NaCl. Known concentration of a given additive was added in small increments into solutions containing EB-DNA complex. After each addition, the mixtures were carefully stirred and allowed to equilibrate for 2 min, followed by recording of the corresponding fluorescence emission spectrum (550–700 nm) upon excitation at 525 nm where the slit widths were 5 nm for both excitation and emission. The changes in the fluorescence emission peak (590 nm) due to EB DNA complex were plotted against the concentrations of each additive. The concentration of additives required to obtain 50% quenching of the maximal fluorescence was used to calculate the binding constant in each case.

References

1. W. TRAUGER, E. E. BAIRD and P. B. DERVAN, *Nature*, 1996, **382**, 559; (b) D. E. WEMMER and P. B. DERVAN, *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.*, 1997, **7**, 355.
2. (a) F. LENG, R. SAVKUR, I. FORK, T. PREZEWOKE, W. PRIEBE and J. B. CHAIRS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **118**, 4731; (b) P. M. TAKAHARA, C. A. FREDERIC and S. J. LIPPARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **118**, 12309; (c) W. D. WILSON, L. RATMEYER, M. ZHAO, L. STREKOVSKI and D. BOYKIN, *Biochemistry*, 1993, **32**, 4098.
3. R. ZITTOUN, *Eur. J. Cancer Clin. Oncol.*, 1985, **21**, 649.
4. M. ACHESON and L. K. ORGEL "The Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds : The Acridines", Interscience, New York, 1956, pp. 362-89.
5. J. ROBINSON and N. OSHEROFF, *Biochemistry*, 1990, **29**, 2511.
6. (a) B. GAUGAIN, J. MARKOVITS, J. B. LE PECQ and B. P. ROQUES, *FEBS Lett.*, 1984, **169**, 123; (b) T. A. GAURDIE, A. S. PRAKASH, L. P. G. WAKELIN, P. D. WOODGATE and W. A. DENNY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, **34**, 240.
7. D. JAYCOX, G. W. GRIBBLE and HACKER, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1987, **24**, 1405.
8. P. KELLY, O. L. PHILIP, R. F. MARTIN and L. P. G. WAKELIN, *Int. J. Pept. Prot. Res.*, 1985, **26**, 400.
9. B. C. BAGUELY, K. M. HOLDAWAY and L. M. FRAY, *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.*, 1990, **82**, 398.
10. E. A. THEODORAKIS, X. XIANG and P. BLOM, *Chem. Commun.*, 1997, 1463.
11. M. SEARCELY, S. MC. CLEAN, B. MADDEN and L. P. G. WAKELIN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1997, 523.
12. C. H. TUNG, A. WEI, M. J. LEIBOWITZ and S. S. STEIN, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1992, **28**, 7114.
13. (a) S. BHATTACHARYA and S. S. MANDAL, *Chem. Commun.*, 1995, 2489; (b) S. S. MANDAL, N. VINAYKUMAR, U. VARSHNEY and S. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1995, **63**, 265; (c) S. S. MANDAL, U. VARSHNEY and S. BHATTACHARYA, *Bioconjugate Chem.*, 1997, **8**, 798.
14. S. BHATTACHARYA and S. S. MANDAL, *Chem. Commun.*, 1996, 1515.
15. S. BHATTACHARYA and S. S. MANDAL, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1997, 29.
16. M. HALL and E. E. TURNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 694.
17. (a) K. YAMAOKA and R. A. RANSIC, *Biopolymers*, 1969, **8**, 289; (b) J. M. CRENSHAW, D. E. GRAVES and W. A. DENNY, *Biochemistry*, 1995, **43**, 13682.
18. *Org. Synth.*, **3**, 53, 54.
19. E. ESTEV and C. H. GAOZZA, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1981, **18**, 1061.
20. O. TSUGE, M. NISHINOHARA and M. TASHIRO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1963, **36**, 1477.
21. T. AKASAKA, SUZUKI, H. OHURI, MEGURO, Y. SHINDO and H. TAKAHASHI, *Anal. Lett.*, 1987, **20**, 1581.
22. (a) B. GAUGAIN, J. MARKOVITS, J. B. LE-PEQ and B. P. ROQUES, *FEBS Lett.*, 1984, **169**, 123; (b) E. K. RAO, Y. BATHNI and J. W. LOWN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 728.
23. (a) D. G. DALGLEISH and A. R. PEACOCKE, *Biopolymers*, 1971, **10**, 1853; (b) W. C. JOHNSON and I. TINOCO, *Biopolymers*, 1969, **7**, 729; (c) H. K. KIM, S. K. KIM, A. RODGER and B. NORDEN, *Biochemistry*, 1996, **35**, 1187.
24. R. J. FIEL and B. R. MUNSON, *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 1980, **8**, 283.
25. (a) R. F. PASTERNAK, E. J. GIBBS and J. J. VILLAFRANCA, *Biochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 2406; (b) W. MULLER, D. M. CROTHERS and M. J. WARING, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1973, 223.
26. (a) D. G. DALGLEISH, H. FUJITA and A. R. PEACOCKE, *Biopolymers*, 1960, **8**, 633; (b) D. G. DALGLEISH, M. C. FIEL and A. R. PEACOCKE, *Biopolymers*, 1972, **11**, 2415.
27. (a) M. J. CARVLIN and R. J. FIEL, *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 1983, **11**, 6121; (b) M. J. CARVLIN, E. MARK and R. FIEL, *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 1983, **11**, 6.
28. T. A. EARLY, D. R. KEARNS, W. HILLEN and R. D. WELLS, *Biochemistry*, 1981, **20**, 3756.
29. W. MULLER and D. M. CROTHERS, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1975, **54**, 267.